

SU(3) Symmetry in hafnium isotopes with even neutron N=100-108

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we have reviewed the calculation of ground states energy level up to spin 14+, electric quadrupole moments up to spin 12+, and reduced transition probabilities of Hafnium isotopes with even neutron $N = 100-108$ by Interacting Boson Model (IBM-1). The calculated results are compared with previous available experimental data and found good agreement for all nuclei. Moreover, we have studied potential energy surface of those nuclei. The systematic studies of quadrupole moments, reduced transition strength, yrast level and potential energy surface of those nuclei show an important property that they are deformed and have dynamical symmetry SU(3) characters.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The interacting boson model offers a simple Hamiltonian, capable of describing collective nuclear properties across a broad range of nuclei, based on general algebraic group theoretical techniques which have also recently found application in problems in atomic, molecular, and high energy physics [1-4]. The three limiting symmetries of this Hamiltonian, U(5), SU(3), and O(6), correspond to the geometrical shapes, spherical vibrator, symmetric rotor, and γ -unstable rotor, respectively [5]. The even-mass Hafnium $^{172-180}\text{Hf}$ isotopes have been extensively investigated experimentally using a wide variety of reactions. The excited states in the even-even $^{172-180}\text{Hf}$ isotopes have been investigated from (γ, γ') , (d, p) , $(\alpha, 2n\gamma)$, $(\alpha, 4n\gamma)$, (n, γ) , $(n, n'\gamma)$ and Coulomb excitation reactions which gave information about the experimental energy levels and the electromagnetic transition probabilities $B(E2)$ in these isotopes [6-15].

In this study, the calculations of energy levels of even-even $^{172-180}\text{Hf}$ isotopes have been done by using interacting boson model. The ground state band, the reduced probabilities of $E2$ transitions ($B(E2)$ values), and electric quadrupole moment Q_L are calculated and compared with available experimental data.

2. THEORETICAL MODEL

2.1 Interacting boson model (IBM)

The IBM-1 Hamiltonian can be expressed as [16, 17]:

$$H = \varepsilon_s(s^\dagger \cdot \tilde{s}) + \varepsilon_d(d^\dagger \cdot \tilde{d}) + \sum_{L=0,2,4} \frac{1}{2} (2L+1) \frac{1}{2} C_L \left[[d^\dagger \times d^\dagger]^{(L)} \times [\tilde{d} \times \tilde{d}]^{(L)} \right]^{(0)} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} v_2 \left[[d^\dagger \times d^\dagger]^{(2)} \times [\tilde{d} \times \tilde{s}]^{(2)} + [d^\dagger \times s^\dagger]^{(2)} \times [\tilde{d} \times \tilde{d}]^{(2)} \right]^{(0)} + \frac{1}{2} v_0 \left[[d^\dagger \times d^\dagger]^{(0)} \times [\tilde{s} \times \tilde{s}]^{(0)} + [s^\dagger \times s^\dagger]^{(0)} \times [\tilde{d} \times \tilde{d}]^{(0)} \right]^{(0)} + \frac{1}{2} u_0 \left[[s^\dagger \times s^\dagger]^{(0)} \times [\tilde{s} \times \tilde{s}]^{(0)} \right]^{(0)} + u_2 \left[[d^\dagger \times s^\dagger]^{(2)} \times [\tilde{d} \times \tilde{s}]^{(2)} \right]^{(0)} \quad (1)$$

Then the IBM-1 Hamiltonian in (1) can be written in general form as [18-20]:

$$\hat{H} = \varepsilon \hat{n}_d + a_0 \hat{P} \cdot \hat{P} + a_1 \hat{L} \cdot \hat{L} + a_2 \hat{Q} \cdot \hat{Q} + a_3 \hat{T}_3 \cdot \hat{T}_3 + a_4 \hat{T}_4 \cdot \hat{T}_4 \quad (2)$$

Where $\hat{n}_d = (s^\dagger, d^\dagger)$ is the total number of d_{boson} operator, $\hat{p} = 1/2 [(d \cdot \tilde{d}) - (s \cdot \tilde{s})]$ is the pairing operator, $\hat{L} = \sqrt{10} [d^\dagger \times \tilde{d}]^1$ is the angular momentum operator, $\hat{Q} = [d^\dagger \times \tilde{s} + s^\dagger \times \tilde{d}]^{(2)} + \chi [d^\dagger \times \tilde{d}]^{(2)}$ is the quadrupole operator (χ is the quadrupole structure parameter and take the values 0 and $\pm \frac{\sqrt{7}}{2}$ [19, 20]), $\hat{T}_r = [d^\dagger \times \tilde{d}]^{(r)}$ is the octupole ($r=3$) and hexadecapole ($r=4$) operator, and $e = e_d - e_s$ is the boson energy. The parameters are a_0 the strength of the pairing, a_1 angular momentum, a_2 quadrupole, a_3 octupole and a_4 hexadecapole interaction between the bosons.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Ground state band

In Figure 1 shows that the even-even $^{174-180}\text{Hf}$ isotopes have a rotational (deformed nuclei) dynamical symmetry SU(3). The rotational limit of the IBM-1 has been applied for the even-even $^{172-180}\text{Hf}$ isotopes due to the values of the $E_{4_1^+}/E_{2_1^+}$ ratio ($E_{4_1^+}/E_{2_1^+} = 3.33$) [19, 20]. The best fitting for the Hamiltonian parameters are presented in Table 1 which gives the best agreement with the experimental data [21-26]. In the framework of the IBM-1, the isotopic chains of Hafnium ($Z = 72$) nuclei, having a number of proton-bosons holes 5, a number of neutron-bosons holes are (9, 10, 11) for even $^{172-176}\text{Hf}$, and (10, 9) for even $^{178-180}\text{Hf}$ isotopes, respectively.

Figure 1. Comparison the IBM-1 calculations with the available experimental data [22-28] of the $E_{4_1^+}/E_{2_1^+}$ ratio for even-even $^{172-180}\text{Hf}$ nuclei.

Table 1. The parameters of even-even ¹⁷²⁻¹⁸⁰Hf nuclei.

Nuclei	N	e MeV	a ₀ MeV	a ₁ MeV	a ₂ MeV	a ₃ MeV	a ₄ MeV	CHQ (χ)
¹⁷² Hf	14	0.00	0.00	0.024	-0.021	0.00	0.00	-1.33
¹⁷⁴ Hf	15	0.00	0.000	0.023	-0.019	0.00	0.00	-1.33
¹⁷⁶ Hf	16	0.00	0.000	0.020	-0.0242	0.00	0.00	-1.33
¹⁷⁸ Hf	15	0.00	0.000	0.021	-0.0258	0.00	0.00	-1.33
¹⁸⁰ Hf	14	0.00	0.000	0.021	-0.0268	0.00	0.00	-1.33

Figure 2 indicates the energy of ground state band in experimental and theoretical data. This figure has shown the IBM-1 calculations for ground band (energies, spin and parity) in good agreement with those of the experimental data [22-28].

Figure 2. Ground state energy level in the IBM-1 calculations and experimental data [22-28] of even-even ¹⁷²⁻¹⁸⁰Hf isotopes.

3.2. B(E2) and Q_L value

The general form of the electromagnetic transitions operator in IBM-1 is [19, 20, 29]:

$$\hat{T}^{(L)} = \gamma_0 [\hat{s}^+ \times \hat{s}^-]^{(0)} + \alpha_2 [\hat{d}^+ \times \hat{s}^- + \hat{s}^+ \times \hat{d}^-]^{(2)} + \beta_L [\hat{d}^+ \times \hat{d}^-]^{(L)} \quad (3)$$

Where γ_0 , α_2 and β_L ($L = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4$) are parameters specifying the various terms in the corresponding operators. Equation (4) yields transition operators for E2 transitions with appropriate values of the corresponding parameters.[19]:

$$T^{E2} = \alpha_2 [d^\dagger s + s^\dagger d]^{(2)} + \beta_2 [d^\dagger d]^{(2)} \quad (4)$$

Where (s^\dagger, d^\dagger) and (s, d) are creation and annihilation operators for s and d bosons, respectively [30], while α_2 and β_2 are two adjustable parameters that measure the strength of each term. The electric transition probabilities, B(E2) values are defined in terms of reduced matrix elements by Iachello and Arima (1987) as [20,29]:

$$B(E2, J_i \rightarrow J_f) = \frac{1}{2J_i + 1} | \langle J_f || T^{E2} || J_i \rangle |^2 \quad (5)$$

For the calculations of the absolute B(E2) values, the parameters, α_2 and β_2 of (4), were adjusted according to reproduce the experimental B(E2; $2_1^+ \rightarrow 0_1^+$). Table 2 shows the values of the α_2 and β_2 parameters, which were obtained in the present calculations. The comparison of calculations values of B(E2) transitions with experimental data[22-29], are given in Table 3, for all isotopes under study.

Table 2. Effective charge (in eb) used to reproduce B(E2) values for ¹⁷²⁻¹⁸⁰Hf nuclei.

	A	N	α_2	β_2
¹⁷² Hf	14	0.1004	-0.2969	
¹⁷⁴ Hf	15	0.0940	-0.2780	
¹⁷⁶ Hf	16	0.0980	-0.2898	
¹⁷⁸ Hf	15	0.0980	-0.2898	
¹⁸⁰ Hf	14	0.1038	-0.3071	

Table 3. The B(E2) values for ¹⁷²⁻¹⁸⁰Hf nuclei (in e²b²).

$J_i \rightarrow J_f$	¹⁷² Hf		¹⁷⁴ Hf		¹⁷⁶ Hf		¹⁷⁸ Hf		¹⁸⁰ Hf	
	IBM-1	EXP.								
2 ₁ ⁺ → 0 ₁ ⁺	0.8748	0.8754	0.8735	0.8775	1.0689	1.0726	0.9493	0.9521	0.9353	0.9361
2 ₂ ⁺ → 0 ₁ ⁺	0.0000	--	0.0000	0.0013	0.0000	0.0005	0.0058	0.0043	0.0073	--
2 ₂ ⁺ → 0 ₂ ⁺	0.6845	--	0.0053	--	0.0059	--	1.3424	--	1.3208	1.3891
2 ₃ ⁺ → 0 ₂ ⁺	0.0270	--	0.7092	--	0.8647	--	0.4562	--	0.4389	--
4 ₁ ⁺ → 2 ₁ ⁺	1.2353	--	1.2351	--	1.5129	--	1.4511	1.3746	1.4242	1.4556
4 ₁ ⁺ → 2 ₂ ⁺	0.0000	--	0.0000	0.0416	0.0000	0.0140	0.8797	--	0.8279	--
4 ₂ ⁺ → 2 ₂ ⁺	0.0294	--	0.4197	--	0.5198	--	1.4776	1.4460	1.4447	1.5099
6 ₁ ⁺ → 4 ₁ ⁺	1.3320	--	1.3352	--	1.6384	--	1.0258	--	0.8430	--
6 ₂ ⁺ → 4 ₂ ⁺	0.7624	--	0.8094	--	1.0047	--	1.4620	1.4817	1.4219	1.4495
8 ₁ ⁺ → 6 ₁ ⁺	1.3512	--	1.3596	--	1.6728	--	1.0652	--	0.9466	--
8 ₂ ⁺ → 6 ₂ ⁺	0.9183	--	0.9438	--	1.1756	--	1.4178	1.7140	1.3692	1.3408
10 ₁ ⁺ → 8 ₁ ⁺	1.3299	--	1.3452	--	1.6611	--	1.0499	--	0.9141	--
10 ₂ ⁺ → 8 ₂ ⁺	0.0278	--	0.9801	--	1.2267	--	1.3593	--	1.3397	--
12 ₁ ⁺ → 10 ₁ ⁺	1.2806	--	1.3045	--	1.6185	--	1.2356	--	1.2179	--
12 ₂ ⁺ → 10 ₂ ⁺	0.9011	--	0.0021	--	0.0022	--	1.2106	--	1.1935	--
2 ₁ ⁺ → 2 ₁ ⁺	1.2529	--	1.2506	--	1.5299	--	1.2012	--	1.1846	--
4 ₁ ⁺ → 4 ₁ ⁺	1.1390	--	1.1368	--	1.3904	--	1.1964	--	1.1803	--
6 ₁ ⁺ → 6 ₁ ⁺	1.1162	--	1.1139	--	1.3618	--	1.1933	--	1.1779	--
8 ₁ ⁺ → 8 ₁ ⁺	1.1078	--	1.1053	--	1.3504	--	0.9493	0.9521	0.9353	0.9361
10 ₁ ⁺ → 10 ₁ ⁺	1.1038	--	1.1008	--	1.3438	--	0.0058	0.0043	0.0073	--
12 ₁ ⁺ → 12 ₁ ⁺	1.1015	--	1.0980	--	1.3386	--	1.3424	--	1.3208	1.3891

Table 3 shows that, in general, most of the calculated results in IBM-1 reasonably consistent with the available experimental data, except for few cases that deviate from the experimental data. The quadrupole moment (Q_L) is an important property for nuclei that can determine if the nucleus is spherical (Q=0), deformed oblate (Q < 0) or prolate (Q > 0) shapes. The electric quadrupole moments of the nuclei can be derived from the transition rate B(E2, L_i → L_f) values according to (6) [31]:

$$Q_L = [16\pi/5]^{1/2} [L(2L - 1)/(2L + 1)(L + 1)(2L + 3)]^{1/2} [B(E2, L_i \rightarrow L_f)]^{1/2} \tag{6}$$

Where L is the angular momentum. Table 4 presents the calculation of the electric quadrupole moment Q_L within the framework of IBM-1 for the even-even Hf nuclei. The presented results for Q_L are compared with previous experimental results [32].

Table 4. The electric quadrupole moment Q_L(in eb)

Q _L	¹⁷² Hf		¹⁷⁴ Hf		¹⁷⁶ Hf		¹⁷⁸ Hf		¹⁸⁰ Hf	
	IBM-1	EXP.	IBM-1	EXP.	IBM-1	EXP.	IBM-1	EXP.	IBM-1	EXP.
2 ₁ ⁺	-1.8971	--	-1.8953	--	-2.0963	-2.10(2)	-1.9759	-2.02(2)	-1.9616	-2.00(2)
2 ₂ ⁺	1.7001	--	1.7141	-	1.9059	-	1.7870	-	1.7639	--
4 ₁ ⁺	-2.4144	--	-2.4121	-	-2.6676	-	-2.5147	-	-2.4966	--
6 ₁ ⁺	-2.6559	--	-2.6531	-	-2.9335	-	-2.7659	-	-2.7463	-
8 ₁ ⁺	-2.7956	--	-2.7924	-	-3.0865	-	-2.9111	-	-2.8908	-
10 ₁ ⁺	-2.8868	--	-2.8829	-	-3.1851	-	-3.0054	-	-2.9851	-
12 ₁ ⁺	-2.9509	--	-2.9461	-	-3.2530	-	-3.0713	-	-3.0514	-

3.3. Potential energy surface (PES)

In recent years, the potential energy surface by Skyrme mean field method was mapped onto the PES of the IBM Hamiltonian[33-36].The expectation value of the IBM-1 Hamiltonian with the coherent state ($|N, \beta, \gamma\rangle$) is used to create the IBM energy surface [20, 37]. The state $|N, \beta, \gamma\rangle$ is a product of boson creation operators (b_c^\dagger) over the boson vacuum $|0\rangle$, i.e.

$$|N, \beta, \gamma\rangle = 1/\sqrt{N!}(b_c^\dagger)^N |0\rangle \quad (7)$$

With

$$b_c^\dagger = (1 + \beta^2)^{-1/2} \left\{ s^\dagger + \beta \left[\cos \gamma (d_0^\dagger) + \sqrt{1/2} \sin \gamma (d_2^\dagger + d_{-2}^\dagger) \right] \right\} \quad (8)$$

The energy surface, as a function of β and γ , has been given by [10]

$$E(N, \beta, \gamma) = \frac{N\varepsilon_d\beta^2}{(1+\beta^2)} + \frac{N(N+1)}{(1+\beta^2)^2} (\alpha_1\beta^4 + \alpha_2\beta^3 \cos 3\gamma + \alpha_3\beta^2 + \alpha_4) \quad (9)$$

Where the α_i 's are related to the coefficients C_L , v_2 , v_0 , u_2 and u_0 of (1). β Measures the total deformation of nucleus, when $\beta = 0$, the shape is spherical, and when $\beta \neq 0$ the shape is distorted. γ is the amount of deviation from the focus symmetry and correlates with the nucleus. If $\gamma = 0$ the shape is prolate, else if $\gamma = 60$ the shape becomes oblate.

The calculated potential energy surfaces for the even-even $^{172-180}\text{Hf}$ are presented in Figure 3. From this figure all nuclei are deformed and have rotational-like characters. The prolate deformation is deeper than oblate in all nuclei.

Figure 3. The potential energy surfaces for even-even $^{172-180}\text{Hf}$ nuclei.

4. CONCLUSION

We have reviewed theoretical calculations of $^{172-180}\text{Hf}$ isotopes with $N=100, 102, 104, 106$ and 108 using IBM-1. The even-even $^{176-180}\text{Hf}$ isotopes have bosons total numbers of 14, 15, 16, 15 and 14. They were considered fully rotational (fully deformed) nuclei, and the dynamical symmetry of these isotopes is $SU(3)$. The low-lying ground states, electric transition probabilities $B(E2)$, and electric quadrupole moment Q_L are obtained for these isotopes using IBM-1 were compared with the available experimental data. A good agreement was obtained between theoretical IBM-1 for all the observables studied. The potential energy surfaces for Hf isotopes show that all nuclei are deformed and have dynamical symmetry $SU(3)$ characters.

APPENDIX

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